

Redefining Traditional Music Theory: Computational Perspectives on Four Fundamental Tonal Colors

Abstract

This article explores the novel finding that musical qualities such as consonance (major or minor) and dissonance (diminished or augmented) stem from the relationship between the fundamental tone and its partials in the overtone series. Dyads and triads are categorized into four distinct types based on this relationship. Given that these harmonic structures constitute the foundational elements of music, this classification can help composers choose the smoothest chord transitions and melodies or enable computers to regulate tonal colors with a high degree of precision that previous music theories cannot produce.

Introduction

The overtone series is fundamental to music because its consonant intervals align with most common scales including the pentatonic and diatonic scales. However, one paradox arises: tones in these scales do not always correspond precisely to the overtone series. For example, A in the C pentatonic or C Lydian scale approximates the 7th or 13th harmonic. Hindemith (1945, 37) argued that harmonics beyond the 7th are unusable due to their inharmonicity. However, according to Zeloni and Pavani (2022), minor second elicits the strongest sadness response in infants, implying an innate human perception of this interval. Moreover, the 15th harmonic composes the minor second, essential for chromaticism despite its harshness. This raises a critical question: Why do certain dissonant intervals—such as the minor second—serve a musical function while others remain unsuitable for traditional music?

Consonance and dissonance have been studied from the perspectives of both nature and nurture. In the nature domain, von Helmholtz's "theory of beats" (1954) and Plomp and Levelt's "critical bandwidth" (1965) are widely regarded as foundational theories. However, they do not fully explain why musicians prefer smaller melodic intervals, as noted by Benward and Saker (2008, 199), nor do they resolve the aforementioned paradox. Additionally, the dissonance curve model—particularly in regards to the relative dissonance of the minor second, tritone, and augmented eighth—exhibit inconsistencies between theoretical predictions and musicians' perceptions (see Sethares, 2004, fig. 6.1, 100; Levine, 1989, fig. 12-7, 98–99). Conversely, from the nurture perspective, Norman Cazden (1945) proposed that consonance perception is culturally conditioned rather than derived from simple intervallic ratios. However, this argument cannot explain the universality of the pentatonic and diatonic scales, as documented by Van Khe (1977). Thus, both perspectives have significant limitations.

This article proposes a different hypothesis: Humans have developed an auditory framework that differentiates between fundamental tones (roots) and partials (non-roots) to facilitate smooth communication. One explanation for why a single tone sounds consonant despite containing potentially dissonant overtones was given by Parncutt (1989, 35), who stated the salience of a pure tone component, or the degree to which it contributes to the perception of complex tones, allows the fundamental to dominate while upper partials blend into timbre. If non-root tones function as outlets for resolving tension within the root tones, then the degree of tension release determines tonal color and function. The terminology of "major" and "minor" intervals appears to reflect this perceptual contrast: intervals with a lower fundamental tone are labeled "major" (e.g., major third, major

second), whereas those with a higher fundamental tone are termed “minor” (e.g., minor second, minor third). Classical musicians likely perceived these intervals as inherently bright or dark, naming them accordingly. Moreover, partial tones generally resolve toward the fundamental, except for the minor third whose fundamental may derive from either the 7th or 13th harmonic. Therefore, the ambiguity between the 7th and 9th harmonics as potential root tones may explain why musicians avoid the 7th harmonic in scale construction as well as augmented eighths and tritones—offering a potential solution to the paradox outlined above.

The novelty of this hypothesis lies in extending the concept of two-root dyads to triads, proposing that three-root triads are the main cause of dissonance in both chords and chord progressions. To test this hypothesis, this article examines triads absent from the diatonic scale, analyzing their frequency across common scales, chords, and progressions. Next, this study employs twelve-tone techniques to classify triads into four categories and assigns each a tonal color, ensuring that neither randomness nor chance accounts for the resulting harmonic cohesion. Finally, it investigates whether tone rows devoid of dissonant triads exhibit a harmonic quality. This hypothesis has significant practical implications for both composition and theory.

Categorizing three-tone triads

If musicians instinctively avoid close or equal tone combinations that lack an outlet for tension resolution, it follows that the pentatonic and diatonic/Lydian scales emerged as structured selections from the overtone series. Within the twelve-tone equal temperament system, certain highly dissonant triads—those containing three root tones—may be identifiable as byproducts of this process. Examining the 19 possible triads not present in the diatonic scale reveals the following particularly dissonant formations:

- 1) 0,1,2 and its transpositions
- 2) 0,1,4 and its transpositions
- 3) 0,3,4 and its transpositions
- 4) 0,4,8 and its transpositions

This suggests that musicians instinctively excluded these triads, much as they avoided incorporating the 7th harmonic into the pentatonic and diatonic scales.

Frequency of three-root triads in scales

It can be speculated that three-root triads are infrequent in common scales if they are indeed responsible for undesirable dissonance in music. By counting only three-root triads and adding one for each in the scales, we can determine their distribution. Chamberlain’s *Musical Scales, Ethnic & Otherwise* (2016, 45–68) lists 202 scales. When 5-tone, 6-tone, and 7-tone scales are reclassified based on the number of three-root triads they contain, the following results emerge. Overlapping scales, such as the major scale (#1) and Lydian scale (#51), are treated as the same.

0 three-root triads

5-tone scales

- 1) 0,2,4,7,9, Pentatonic scale. #158, #164, #191, #192, #197
- 2) 0,2,3,7,8, Hirajoshi scale. #157, #162, #173, #178, #184

- 3) 0,2,3,7,9, Kumoi scale. #159, #163, #167, #186, #190
- 4) 0,4,5,7,11, Pelong/Ryukyu scale. #155, #156, #179, #180, #183
- 5) 0,2,5,7,11, Hindu pentatonic scale. #153, #161, #181, #187, #189
- 6) 0,2,4,7,11, Indian/Bulgarian/Javanese scale. #160, #182, #194
- 7) 0,2,4,7,10, African/Japanese/Korean kyemyonjo scale. #154, #166, #196
- 8) 0,2,3,7,10, African scale. #185, #198

6-tone scales

- 1) 0,2,4,5,7,9, Irish/Greek/Scotch scale. #64, #72, #75, #87, #92, #95, #96, #101, #103
- 2) 0,2,4,6,7,9, Lydian 6 tone. #68, #77, #86, #90, #99, #102
- 3) 0,2,4,6,7,11, Abuselic/Samanta scale. #71, #74
- 4) 0,2,3,7,9,10, Akebono scale. # 73, #88, #93
- 5) 0,2,3,5,7,9, Hungarian/Scotch scale. #94, #100
- 6) 0,4,5,7,9,10, Polish scale. #85

1 three-root triad

5-tone scales

- 1) 0,1,4,6,10, Diminished pentatonic scale. #169, #170
- 2) 0,1,4,7,10, Pentatonic dominant scale. #176
- 3) 0,2,4,6,10, Jazz pentatonic scale. #193

2 three-root triads

5-tone scales

- 1) 0,1,5,7,9, Japanese pentatonic scale. #165, #171, #195
- 2) 0,4,6,8,11, Japanese pentatonic scale. #168
- 3) 0,1,4,6,9, Vibhasa scale. #172
- 4) 0,3,4,7,10, Pentatonic dominant scale. #174
- 5) 0,2,5,6,10, Japanese pentatonic scale. #188

6-tone scales

- 1) 0,3,5,7,9,11, African scale. #65
- 2) 0,1,4,6,9,11, Panchana scale. #78
- 3) 0,1,4,6,7,10, Combined-Altered scale. #81
- 4) 0,1,4,5,7,10, Greek scale. #84
- 5) 0,2,6,7,9,10, Overtone 6 tone scale #89
- 6) 0,2,5,7,8,11, Armenian Ancient Church scale. #91
- 7) 0,2,4,6,8,10, Whole Tone scale. #97
- 8) 0,2,4,6,7,10, Prometheus scale. 98#

3 three-root triads

5-tone scales

- 1) 0,1,4,7,8, Rewa scale. #175
- 2) 0,1,4,7,9, Scriabin's scale. #177

6-tone scales

- 1) 0,3,5,6,7,10, Blues scale. #66
- 2) 0,1,3,6,8,10, Vilasakhani scale. #67
- 3) 0,1,3,6,9,10, Hidshaf scale, #69
- 4) 0,1,3,5,8,11, Gurjari scale, #70
- 5) 0,1,3,5,7,9, African scale, #76

4 three-root triads

- 1) 0,1,4,6,9,10, Prometheus Neapolitan scale, #79

5 three-root triads

- 1) 0,1,4,5,7,8, Bangala scale, #83

6 three-root triads

- 1) 0,3,4,7,8,11, Augmented scale, #80, #82

Among 7-tone scales, only the diatonic one lacks any three-root triads, and thus, 7-tone scales are not reclassified.

Three-root triads analysis in chord transitions

If the primary source of dissonance in chord progressions stems from three-root triads, these triads are expected to appear frequently in inharmonic chord transitions, such as from C to F#m. The number of three-root triads between the preceding and following chords is examined using the following rule:

Rule: If the triads 0, 1, 2 and all of their transpositions, 0, 1, 4 and all of their transpositions, 0, 3, 4 and all of their transpositions, or 0, 4, 8 and all of their transpositions are found between the two chords, they are counted, with one added for each occurrence.

For example, when moving from C to Cm, the following triads appear: 0, 3, 4; 3, 4, 7; and 0, 4, 8. This transition is counted as +3.

Exceptional rule: If a chromatic motion occurs involving either a minor third or major third interval that moves to the same size of the interval, three-root triads are not counted. For example, if 0,4 moves to 1,5, 0,1,4 and 1,4,5 are not counted as +1. In his work Laitz (2019, 624) considered that chromatic sequences tend to feature chords with similar qualities. Although the concept differs slightly from the subject of this paper, chromatic motions are known to facilitate smooth chord transitions without introducing dissonance among musicians. We examined the transition from C to C, Cm, C dim, Csus4, C7 and all their respective transitions. The following results were obtained:

0 three-root triad

- 1) C, 2) Csus4, 3) C7,
- 4) D, 5) Dm, 6) Dsus4, 7) D7,
- 8) Em, 9) E dim, 10) Esus4,
- 11) F, 12) Fsus4,

- 13) F# dim,
- 14) G, 15) Gm, 16) Gsus4, 17) G7,
- 18) Am, 19) Asus4,
- 20) Bb , 21) Bmb ,
- 22) Bm, 23) B dim, 24) Bsus4,

1 three-root triad

- 1) C dim,
- 2) C#, 3) C# dim,
- 4) D dim,
- 5) Eb dim,
- 6) Fm
- 7) G dim,
- 8) Bb dim, 9) Bb 7,
- 10) B, 11) B7,

2 three-root triads

- 1) Cm,
- 2) Eb , 3) Emb , 4) Eb 7,
- 5) F#, 6) F#m, 7) F#sus4, 8) F#7,
- 9) A, 10) A dim, 11) A7,

3 three-root triads

- 1) C#m, 2) C#sus4,
- 3) F dim, 4) F7,
- 5) Bb sus4

4 three-root triads

- 1) C#7,
- 2) Eb sus4,
- 3) E, 4) E7,
- 5) G#, 6) G# dim, 7) G#7,

5 three-root triads

- 1) G#m, 2) G#sus4,

Constructing four types of twelve-tone rows

1) Triad classification

If tonal colors in triads are determined by the smooth relationships among three tones, it can be hypothesized that triads lacking a non-root tone as an outlet are the most dissonant—these are the previously mentioned three-root triads. By contrast, triads containing one root tone and two non-root tones are believed to sound brighter due to the smoother transitions among tones. When triads contain two root tones, the outlet becomes less fluid, resulting in a darker sound than major triads. Finally, triads without any root tones are considered dissonant due to internal tension; however,

unlike three-root triads, their influence dissipates faster, rendering them less dissonant. This classification yields four statistical combinations of root and non-root tones, each defining a modality.

2) Classification of major and minor triads

Major chords can be constructed by adding tones derived from partials to the perfect fifth, aligning with the flow of the diatonic/Lydian scale as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Moreover, some triads with root tone C can be constructed from those tetrachords. Thus, those can be classified as major triads which consist of the fundamental tone C and its partials.

- 1) 0,7,9
- 2) 0,7,11
- 3) 0,2,7
- 4) 0,2,11
- 5) 0,4,7
- 6) 0,2,4

By contrast, minor triads likely feature one tone exerting greater influence than the fundamental due to its wider interval. This suggests the presence of two root tones, giving minor chords a darker quality. Riemann (1897, 10) proposed the hypothetical concept of the undertone, a symmetrical counterpart to the major mode (see Figure 3). Although scientists like Helmholtz (1875, 365) dismissed this theory, arguing that undertones do not exist physically, Riemann's (1897) notion of symmetry remains relevant: minor mode structures feature influential intervals occurring after the fundamental, contrasting the diatonic/Lydian scale's natural progression.

Thus, minor triads can be derived as illustrated in Figure 2:

Figure 2

From the last tetrachord, the following triads emerge, mirroring the symmetry of major triads except for 0, 2, 4.

- 1) 0,2,9
- 2) 0,5,7
- 3) 0,4,9

- 4) 0,4,11
- 5) 0,9,11

Figure 3

Top triads are major triads. C is the fundamental tone and the rest are partial tones.
 Bottom triads are minor triads with a structure symmetric to major triads.

3) Classification of triad 0,1,2 as a melody line

Although this functions as a three-root tone and is dissonant as a chord, as a melody, it exhibits a kaleidoscopic effect due to its small intervals. When it moves chromatically, it lacks major or minor characteristics. However, if the non-root tones transition to root tones, the motion is classified as major due to its smooth progression from non-root (dominant) to root (tonic). Conversely, motion in the opposite direction is classified as minor mode. Thus, the smoothness of tonal flow determines color. The melody line of 0, 1, 2 can be classified as follows:

- 1) 0,1,2 diminished mode
- 2) 0,2,1, minor mode
- 3) 1,0,2, minor mode
- 4) 1,2,0, major mode
- 5) 2,0,1, major mode
- 6) 2,1,0 diminished mode

4) Constructing four types of twelve-tone rows

Rule 1: Dyads are excluded due to their instability.

Rule 2: Although the set {0, 5, 7} is classified as minor, it is possible to use it in the major mode due to its weak color.

Rule 3: The sets {1, 0, 2} and the set {2, 0, 1} are excluded due to their weak color.

Rule 4: The following triads define the four modal categories:

Major

- 1) The set {0, 4, 7} and all transpositions
- 2) The set {0, 4, 5} and all transpositions
- 3) The set {0, 2, 5} and all transpositions

- 4) The set {0, 2, 7} and 12 transpositions
- 5) The set {0, 5, 7} and all transpositions
- 6) The set {0, 2, 4} and all transpositions
- 7) The set {0, 1, 3} and all transpositions
- 8) The set {1, 2, 0} and 12 transpositions

Minor

- 1) The set {0, 3, 7} and all transpositions
- 2) The set {0, 1, 5} and all transpositions
- 3) The set {0, 3, 5} and all transpositions
- 4) The set {0, 5, 7} and 12 transpositions
- 5) The set {0, 2, 3} and all transpositions
- 6) The set {0, 2, 1} and 12 transpositions

Augmented

- 1) The set {0, 4, 8} and all transpositions
- 2) The set {0, 3, 4} and all transpositions
- 3) The set {0, 1, 4} and all transpositions

Diminished

- 1) The set {0, 1, 2} and 12 transpositions
- 2) The set {0, 3, 6} and all transpositions

Rule 5: Twelve-tone rows are constructed to ensure that at any truncation point, the resulting triads remain within a single category. For example, in the tone row 0, 11, 4, 6, 5, the triads 0, 11, 4 (a transposition of 0,1,5), 11, 4, 6 (a transposition of 0,5,7) and 4, 6, 5 (a transposition of 0,2,1) all belong to the minor category. This principle is applied consistently.

Below are examples of constructed twelve-tone rows. Additional details are available in the code repository listed in Appendix.

Major mode: Approximately, 400 twelve tone rows and these are some of them:

- a) 0,10,3,5,1,6,8,4,11,9,2,7
- b) 0,4,5,7,3,8,10,6,11,1,9,2
- c) 0,10,8,3,5,1,11,6,4,2,7,9
- d) 0,5,10,7,3,1,8,6,4,9,2,11

Minor mode: There are six twelve tone rows and these are some of them:

- a) 0,11,4,6,5,10,1,3,2,7,9,8
- b) 0,10,7,9,8,6,3,5,4,2,11,1

Augmented mode: There are two twelve tone rows:

- a) 0,8,4,5,1,9,10,6,2,3,11,7
- b) 0,1,9,10,6,2,3,11,7,8,4,5

Diminished mode: There is only one twelve tone row:

- a) 0,1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11

Moreover, major mode a), minor mode a), and augmented mode a) can be harmonized in two ways: with or without three-root triads. While computational methods exist, the following rows were manually constructed.

Sample A-1-①

Sample A-1-②

Sample A-2-①

Sample A-2-②

Sample A-3-①

Sample A-3-②

Discussion

One intriguing observation is that a clear distinction exists between scales without three-root triads and those that contain them. Scales lacking three-root triads tend to be used across various cultures

and often appear in different modes. Their tonal application depends on the starting tone or tonal colors. Especially, among seventy-five six-note pitch-class sets, only six lack three-root triads, and all are employed as scales, as listed above. By contrast, scales with three-root triads are almost always culture-specific, with limited flexibility in their starting tone and mode.

According to Van Khe (1977, 83), the pentatonic scale—the most commonly employed scale appears even in cultures that have developed a wide range of scales. This suggests that musicians initially favored consonant scales before exploring more dissonant ones, much like Western composers who progressively developed their compositions toward atonal music. Thus, unlike mildly dissonant intervals such as the minor second or major second, which maintain a root and non-root relationship, musicians tend to avoid employing dissonant triads with three tones. This likely explains why scales without three-root triads frequently overlap across cultures, while those containing three-root triads remain more restricted in their usage.

If musicians instinctively prefer scales without three-root tones, it follows that they also avoid using such chords frequently. Arthurs, Beeston, and Timmers (2018, 11) examined the frequency of chord types in Bach's *Italianisches Konzert* BWV 971 and The Beatles' 30 best-selling UK hits (see Fig. 5). Their findings confirm that while chords containing three-root triads—such as augmented triads, minor-major seventh, chords and augmented major seventh chords—do appear, they are significantly less frequent than commonly employed chords. Likewise, Kantarelis et al. (2024, 4) analyzed a dataset of 666,000 songs, yielding comparable results (see Table 2). Although the chord type “Augmented” appears 27,400 times, this is considerably less frequent than “Major” (36,331,613 occurrences) and “Minor” (13,104,882 occurrences). These findings indicate that musicians in tonal compositions prefer chords without three-root tones over those that include them.

How do three-root triads function in chord transitions? Willey and Cabral (2007, 5) analyzed the chord transitions of Brazilian composer Antônio Carlos Jobim (see Figure 5). Their results suggest that as the number of three-root triads in a transition increases, their usage decreases. Although transitions containing three-root triads—like C to C#7—occur, they are typically employed for modulation rather than as common progressions. It is rare for G#m or G#sus4 to follow C. Moreover, Hooktheory (2025) reports similar findings: chord transitions like C to E or C to A, involving three-root triads, primarily serve modulation purposes rather than conventional progressions like dominant-to-tonic movement. This reinforces the idea that musicians instinctively prefer not only scales and chords but also chord progressions that avoid three-root triads.

Furthermore, as the hypothesis predicted, twelve-tone rows structured around triads of a single category tend to exhibit four distinct harmonic colors. The perceptual difference between major and minor twelve-tone rows seems to stem from whether the tone flow aligns with the diatonic/Lydian scale or its inverse. Rosner (1992, 407) stated that “listeners never equated the harmonic closure of perfect authentic cadences with that of plagal ones.” While this distinction applies to V–I versus I–V progressions, it is significant because the tonal color differences between the major and minor modes result from the same structural principles. By contrast, the “muddy” quality of Sample A-1-②, Sample A-2-②, and Sample A-3-② can be attributed to their deviation from the diatonic scale. Additionally, although a minor second consists of a root and non-root combination, raising the upper tone by an octave creates an augmented octave (eighth), which exhibits a two-root quality due to pitch height differences. This structural positioning is particularly effective as a starting melody in Sample A-3, further reinforcing unique tonal colors. These findings suggest that, in terms of sound, the realm beyond tonality is not chaotic but as orderly as tonal music. Consequently, both dissonance and consonance can be mechanically controlled.

If this is the case, why has the realm beyond tonality not been recognized as an orderly system, similar to tonality? This seems to be related to the instability of smaller intervals. For example,

although this perspective is subjective, blue-circled tones within a particular tone row (Figure 4) resemble the major mode due to the influence of triads 10,8,6 and 6,4,2.

Figure 4

This phenomenon extends to other twelve-tone rows. It can be speculated that the higher a tone appears in the overtone series, the more quickly it dissipates, and tonal color strength seems to follow a similar pattern. Due to this instability, three-root triads sometimes resemble the minor mode depending on the context. For example, in the following passage within the red rectangle (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Chasselon, Mélanie. *Nocturne, "Abandon"*. 1873. Heugel et Cie.

Although Eb, G, and F# form a three-root triad, they sound like a minor mode because the tones consistently move from root to non-root, concluding with a chromatic ending typical of the minor mode. The melody line G, F#, Ab exhibits the same pattern. By contrast, this effect seldom occurs in triads containing lower intervals like the perfect fifth, which contributes to the relative stability of twelve-tone rows in Sample A-1 and Sample A-2. Additionally, without a hierarchical relationship between two tones, a stable tonal structure cannot be established. These factors likely explain why, in terms of perception, the realm beyond tonality has not been considered an ordered system.

The significance of these findings

If the hypothesis that three-root triads result from the 12-tone equal temperament system, are more dissonant than other tone combinations like the minor second or tritone, and maintain the same degree of order as the tonal realm is correct, then it is possible to create an algorithm to construct musical elements such as modulations by controlling three-root triads. However, this requires additional parameters such as consonance and tension, which this paper does not address. Regarding modulations, if this pitch class is applied to modulation generation, the following formula can be used::

$X = \text{IntermediateChord}(Y, Z),$

where Y and Z represent the chords to be combined, particularly distant ones such as C and D \flat m or C and G#m. X consists of all possible chords (totaling 3,969, excluding dyads). A computer can then select the most consonant chords among them.

We show some results below:

Sample B-1

Sample B-2

By contrast, if three-root triads are intentionally included, the result is this:

Sample C

Comparing these examples reveals subtle but noticeable differences between Sample B, which lacks three-root triads, and Sample C, which includes them. Furthermore, since dyads and triads serve as fundamental building blocks of musical composition, this concept is also applicable to algorithms for generating musical elements such as arpeggios, scales, harmonizations, and melodies. For implementation details, refer to the code repository listed in the Appendix.

Moreover, this concept provides composers with a technique to achieve a coherent sound quality in twelve-tone compositions, regardless of consonance or dissonance.

For example, consider the main theme of Anton Webern's *Kinderstück, Opus M267* (1949, Carl Fischer).

Sample D-1

This melody contains tonal elements. Slightly altering the melody line to fit within a tonal framework produces the following result (Figure 6):

Figure 6

E \flat , E, C, B, B \flat , C#, D, A, G#, G, F#, F

E \flat , E, C, B, B \flat , D, C#, A, G#, F, G, F#

Moreover, modifying the rhythm in this manner transforms the composition into what sounds like entirely tonal music, despite its atonal structure.

Sample D-2

Thus, this concept enables musicians to control tonal color within atonal music, whether consonant or dissonant.

Limitations

No previous theory has posited that the relationship between the fundamental tone (root) and partials (non-root) determines the color and function of chords or chord progressions, the tritone, in particular, presents challenges. Although this close interval appears as the 11th harmonic in the overtone series, Deutsch (1991) found that listeners struggle to determine whether a tritone is ascending or descending. This suggests that its tonal weight is balanced between two tones. Its classification can be examined through its functional differences. Rosner (1992, 408) states that “VII (diminished chord) very frequently functions as dominant (leading-tone chord, down a third from V)”. By contrast, Aldwell and Schachter (2002, 547–548) argue that “In all cases, the augmented quality results from voice-leading activity: The augmented triad expands or represents a major or minor triad; it does not function as a self-sufficient harmonic entity.”

The tritone appears to align with the characteristics of the non-root tone combination, as it dissipates quickly when followed by another tone. Moreover, the diminished triad is less dissonant than the augmented triad or augmented eighth (Roberts 1986, 170; Levine 1989, 98–99) and occurs within the diatonic scale. From this perspective, the tritone cannot be classified as a two-root combination. However, the mechanism of how the non-root combination occurs remains unresolved. Due to this, certain triads containing a tritone, like 0,2,6 or 0,6,7, are difficult to categorize as either major or minor. Empirical observations suggest that 0,2,6 and 0,6,7 align with major tonalities, while 0,4,6 and 0,1,7 align with minor. However, no evidence supports this claim, necessitating further research.

In contrast, although the characteristics of root tone combinations seem to offer high predictability of inharmonic chords or chord transitions such as C to C#m, they also present inconsistencies in perceived dissonance. For example, comparing the transition from C to C#m with that of C#m to C reveals that the latter sounds smoother than the former. A major triad tends to sound more stable than a minor triad when following a chord transition entailing three-root triads. Similarly, dominant seventh chords and diminished triads appear resistant to three-root triad dissonance, allowing for greater flexibility in modulation. This suggests that dissonance levels vary depending on the subsequent chord. Chords with weaker roots seem more resistant to dissonance, warranting further investigation.

Moreover, this system does not explore the microtonal realm or multiple tone combinations due to the above-mentioned difficulty. In the microtonal realm, the tone relationship is more subtle and comparable to a seesaw that strikes the balance between right and left. Moreover, if the tones are piled up, the balance is altered and dissonant chords occasionally exhibit a consonant sound. Levine (1989, 99) claims that “Minor ninths sound consonant in some situations, highly dissonant in others”. Because of the tones used in traditional music scales that do not always fit into the 12-tone equal temperament system and the effect of tones and tone combinations in the microtonal realm, the results for frequencies of three-root triads in scales might be biased and requires further research. Additionally, exploring this uncharted territory might benefit the development of new scales or tuning systems.

Furthermore, in actual composition, controlling tonal colors as proposed in this paper does not always guarantee ideal harmonization. For example, modifying the harmony in Sample E-2 reveals that the chord progression Dm–Gm does not align well with the melody, despite being one of the most consonant motions.

Consider Rentaro Taki, *Regret* (1903, Zenon Publisher).

Sample E-1

Sample E-2

Conversely, jazz compositions frequently feature dissonant chord progressions that perfectly complement their melodies. This suggests that harmonization issues may stem from tonal imbalances rather than dissonance alone. Understanding the mechanisms of tonal colors alone is therefore insufficient—harmonization requires assessing the balance between melody and harmony. Hence, this area also requires further research.

Overall, this study results in a small sample size for this study and does not include empirical testing through listener surveys or perceptual experiments. This paper also does not provide extensive references to existing literature supporting the hypothesis, as an independent researcher, I have limited access to institutional resources and large-scale datasets. Moreover, no prior theory has proposed similar hypothesis. The novelty of the hypothesis naturally limits the availability of direct theoretical precedents, positioning this work as an initial step toward a new line of inquiry. In order to validate this hypothesis, particularly the legitimacy of three-root triads this paper have proposed, it is necessary to examine and analyze the compositions of over 50 composers from various musical periods. As such, further research is necessary to empirically validate the theoretical claims and assess their perceptual implications in broader musical contexts.

To conclude, the structure of major triads aligns with the overtone series, wherein the fundamental tone is followed by partial tones, containing one root and two non-roots. Conversely, minor triads exhibit the opposite structure, with a wider interval following the fundamental tone, resulting in two roots. Unlike these consonant formations, dissonant three-root triads do not appear in the diatonic scale and are the most dissonant because all their tones tend to persist, causing dissonance in chord progressions, scales, and chords. By contrast, three-non-root triads dissipate more quickly, making them less dissonant and functionally dominant.

Thus, in this framework, the sound of “the atonal realm” is as structured and predictable as the tonal realm, unlike Schoenberg’s compositional techniques. Therefore, it is possible to algorithmically generate musical elements such as consonant twelve-tone rows or chord progressions by controlling the atonal realm. Due to its high predictability in tonal color, this concept has the potential to help develop more advanced algorithms capable of generating compositions indistinguishable from those created by humans.

Appendix

The software is available at:

<https://apps.microsoft.com/store/detail/9NRDXQKZL993?cid=DevShareMCLPCS>

(Note: the parameters employed in this system differ slightly from those discussed in this article to accommodate practical composition requirements).

References

1. Aldwell, Edward, and Carl Schachter. *Harmony & Voice Leading*. 3rd ed. Thomson Schirmer, 2002.
2. Arthurs, Yuko, Amy V. Beeston, and Renee Timmers. “Perception of Isolated Chords: Examining Frequency of Occurrence, Instrumental Timbre, Acoustic Descriptors, and Musical Training.” *Psychology of Music* 46, no. 5 (2018): 662-681.
3. Benward, Bruce, and Marilyn Saker. *Music in Theory and Practice*. 8th ed., vol. 1. Boston: Higher Education Press, 2008.
4. Cazden, Norman. “Musical Consonance and Dissonance: A Cultural Criterion.” *The Journal of Aesthetics and Art Criticism* 4, no. 1 (1945): 3-11.
5. Chamberlain, Joelee. “Musical Scales, Ethnic & Otherwise” Volume 1: A Short-Cut to Identifying and Using Scales, Based on Their Relationships to the Major Scale Plus Various Interesting Oddities. United States, January 5, 2023.
6. Deutsch, Diana. “The Tritone Paradox: An Influence of Language on Music Perception.” *Music Perception* 8, no. 4 (1991): 335-347.
7. Hindemith, Paul. *The Craft of Musical Composition*. 4th ed. Translated by A. Mendel, Inc. 1945. London: Schott & Co., Ltd. New York: Associated Music Publishers.
8. Hooktheory. “I Analyzed the Chords of 1300 Popular Songs for Patterns. This Is What I Found.” Accessed February 2, 2025. <https://www.hooktheory.com/blog/music-theory-analysis-1300-songs-for-songwriting-part2/>.

9. Kantarelis, Spyridon, Konstantinos Thomas, Vassilis Lyberatos, Edmund Dervakos, and Giorgos Stamou. CHORDONOMICON: A Dataset of 666,000 Songs and Their Chord Progressions. Greece: Artificial Intelligence and Learning Systems Laboratory, National Technical University of Athens, October 2024.
10. Laitz, Steven. *The Complete Musician: An Integrated Approach to Tonal Theory, Analysis, and Listening*. 4th ed. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2019.
11. Levine, Mark. *The Jazz Piano Book*. Petaluma, CA: Sher Music Co., 1989.
12. Plomp, R., and W. J. M. Levelt. "Tonal Consonance and Critical Bandwidth." Institute for Perception RVO-TNO, Soesterberg, Netherlands. Received April 26, 1965.
13. Pamcutt, Richard. *Harmony: A Psychoacoustic Approach*. Edited by Helmut K. V. Lotsch. Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag, 1989.
14. Riemann, Hugo. *Harmony Simplified: Or the Theory of the Tonal Functions of Chords*. 2nd ed. translated from the German. London: Augener Limited, 1897.
15. Roberts, L. A. "Consonance Judgements of Musical Chords by Musicians and Untrained Listeners." *Acustica* 62 (1986): 163-171. Murray Hill, NJ: AT&T Bell Laboratories.
16. Rosner, Burton S., and Eugene Narmour. "Harmonic Closure: Music Theory and Perception." *Music Perception* 9, no. 4 (1992): 383-411.
17. Sethares, William A., *Timbre Tuning, Spectrum, and Scale*. 2nd ed. Berlin: Springer, 2004.
Van Khe, Tran. "Is the Pentatonic Universal? A Few Reflections on Pentatonism." *The World of Music* 19, no. 1/2 (1977): 76-84.
18. von Helmholtz, Hermann. *On the Sensations of Tone*. Translated by A. J. Ellis. London: Dover, 1954.
19. Willey, Robert, and Giordano Cabral. *Representing Antônio Carlos Jobim's Harmonic Progressions*. School of Music, University of Louisiana at Lafayette, 2007.
20. Zeloni, G., and F. Pavani. "Minor Second Intervals: A Shared Signature for Infant Cries and Sadness in Music." *I-Perception*, 13, no. 2 (2022): 1-10.

5,247 words